

Boreal Avian Modelling (BAM) Project

Predictive tools for the monitoring and assessment of boreal birds in
Canada, 2012-2013

2012–2013 Annual Report to Environment Canada

2012–2013 Annual Report

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Highlights of Accomplishments 2012 – 2013

- Addition of avian point count data across Canada and the United States as it becomes available. Data received from Quebec BBS data, Minnesota and Alaska additions, as well as some recent Canada Warbler status data in Alberta. Version 3.0 of the avian database contains over 250,000 sampling events from over 120 projects.
- Improvements made to correct the Common Attribute Scheme for Forest Resource Inventory (cross-walked coverage of FRI across Canada) for differences in tree and shrub species codes.
- A manuscript on analyses that assess the relative importance of 131 biophysical predictor variables on avian abundance accepted for publication following revision.
- Maps of predicted distributions of 88 boreal species and relative habitat suitability posted to BAM website.
- Database of estimated avian densities as a function of forest type and age in Alberta, using detailed forest inventory information, posted on the BAM website.
- Development of prototype boreal-wide habitat association models for 3 boreal species (Canada Warbler, Connecticut Warbler and Black-throated Green Warbler), using the BAM point count database, and CASFRI biophysical dataset combined with BAM methods to account for differences in sampling protocol and detectability. Comparison of habitat associations between eastern and western ranges in Canada were conducted..
- Further development of forestry management simulation platform (Tardis) that allows BAM to determine detailed forest characteristics (age and species composition, site index, density, soil moisture) across the forested area of Canada and allows incorporation of data concerning fire

history or protected areas specification. These results were used in preliminary simulation modelling to predict the structure and distribution of forests through time and space and will be used in predicting avian response to habitat change .

- Development of bioclimatic niche models of current avian distribution and density for 102 native songbird species (74 boreal species) across Canada and Alaska for use in estimating avian response to climate change. . Potential for these species to shift their ranges and change their abundance across North America’s boreal region in response to projected climate change was assessed, as well as identification of potential refugia.
- Scientific support and access to data for EC projects provided including the evaluation of a monitoring program design for songbirds in four proposed National Wildlife Areas in NWT, and, Effects Assessment Monitoring under the Joint Oil Sands Monitoring program.
- Spatially-explicit models of density and distribution for Canada Warbler at a regional (north-western Alberta) scale were generated to assist in land use planning, and a methodology applicable to other species and regions.
- Identification of potential conservation allowances for Canada Warbler in north-western Alberta based on Marxan analysis.
- Species abundance for waterfowl species in relation to biophysical variables modelled, and ranges compared to NatureServe range maps, using methodology developed by BAM. Population dynamics for several species of waterfowl were studied for the western part of Canada, including population growth rates and effects of seasonality.
- Symposium hosted during the North American Ornithological Conference, 2012, titled “Assessing bird populations at regional to continental scales” and included 12 presentations to an audience of approximately 150.
- Updated website content (in English and French) posted to reflect advances in methodologies, new maps and results, and to describe application of BAM results in conservation efforts by partners.
- Project results communicated to scientist and managers through scientific papers (3 published, 5 in press, 10 in preparation in 2011-2012), technical reports (2) and presentations (20) (as well as the website).

1.0 Project Description and Objectives

Across Canada's boreal forest, management efforts are hampered by a lack of information on birds and their habitats. The boreal region is a key breeding area for many of North America's migratory landbirds. This region is rapidly changing under the increasing pressure of industrial development and climate change. Before the BAM Project was initiated, little coherent knowledge existed at large spatial scales about the density, distribution, and habitat needs of avian populations and communities, and little ability to effectively predict the effects of threats to species or assess the efficacy of management actions directed at mitigating negative impacts.

The purpose of the Boreal Avian Modelling (BAM) Project is to develop and disseminate reliable, quantitative, and predictive models of the distribution and abundance of boreal birds and to facilitate model applications to avian conservation and management. Specific applications include land-use planning, design and implementation of monitoring programs, current and future population status assessment, environmental impact assessment, recovery and action planning for Species At Risk, and protected areas planning and management. Fundamental to our work has been the systematic assembly and integration of the most comprehensive set of observational data possible, modelled using the best available environmental covariates and advanced statistical methodologies. The observational data come from a multitude of studies conducted by scientists in government, environmental non-governmental organisations, industry and academia, working across the boreal and hemi-boreal regions of North America, over the past 20 years.

The continued success of the Boreal Avian Modelling Project depends on maintaining strong partnerships with individuals and organisations contributing avian data and environmental covariates, as well as related expertise, and the critical support of funding partners.

The **BAM project objectives** are to:

- Assemble and maintain a repository, as complete and current as possible, of spatially-referenced data for boreal birds and their habitats.
- Apply and refine state-of-the art analytical methods to:
 - Provide reliable information on boreal bird habitat associations,
 - Describe species distributions and abundances,
 - Refine and forecast population status and trends, and
 - Generate testable hypotheses about key mechanisms underlying the observed spatial and temporal variation (e.g., climate, land use, latitude, vegetation).
- Improve the standardisation and rigor of avian data collection by providing standards for bird sampling protocols and database structure.
- Provide a conservation legacy for avian data collected in North America's boreal forest beyond the original study purposes.
- Build support from academia, industry, governments, non-governmental organisations, and other interested parties for further development and testing of boreal bird population models and other

decision-support tools, and to foster their proactive application to the management of boreal forests and biodiversity conservation.

- Encourage public awareness and support education by providing ready access to current information on the status of boreal bird populations.

This report summarises work undertaken between June 21, 2012 and March 31, 2013 as funded by the Environment Canada Contribution Agreement to BAM.

2.0 Accomplishments

2.1 Database Maintenance and Enhancement

The BAM avian point-count database continues to expand, both in sample size and spatial coverage, as we solicit and accept new avian point-count data from existing and new regional survey programs. We expanded our study region to include the boreal and hemiboreal region in Canada and extending into Alaska and areas of the northern states.

Between June 2012 and March 2013, we received and are in the process of incorporating the following new datasets into our comprehensive database:

- new databases from Alaska representing 10 different projects ;
- Québec Breeding Bird Atlas data;
- Minnesota data (representing 21 years, hemiboreal region);
- 1176 point-count locations from northwestern Alberta used for the Canada Warbler status assessment (see Section 2.4.1) and 1136 points counts from CWS activities under Joint Oil Sands Monitoring (see Section 2.3.2), collected in 2012 ;
- New England data with 384 locations in the hemiboreal;
- All Canadian BBS data.

Current statistical analyses are making use of this most recent version of the dataset. We still anticipate receiving data from Nunavut and Newfoundland. We are working with the Environment Canada to collate data from the remaining studies from Yukon Territory.

The avian database contains over 250,000 sampling events, with data from more than 120 different projects from across Canada, Alaska, and into northern continental US.

Major additions to the biophysical dataset have not been made over the past year. However, significant improvements have been made to the CASFRI dataset. The CASFRI integrates Forest Resource Inventories (FRIs) held by industry and governments from across Canada into a common attribute schema (CAS). Figure 1 shows the coverage of the CASFRI data, as well as the age of the aerial

photography used to prepare the FRI. The CASFRI forest data allowed the team to define consistent habitat classification and forest age variables within the study area covered by the CASFRI.

Figure 1: Coverage of CASFRI data, showing mean age of air photography used in the component inventories.

Because we have not had the resources to perform a rigorous quality control on the CASFRI product, we have relied on error-checking conducted during the course of using the dataset. Over the 2012 fiscal year, as we began to move from CASFRI development to application, we discovered a number of bugs in the standards definition, the translation protocol, and the computer codes that implemented these. The most serious bugs related to the implementation of the standardized tree and shrub species codes and the proportional abundances of tree species within forest canopy layers (species compositions). Thousands of exceptions to the species composition rules were detected in May 2012, and were exhaustively corrected. In September and October, we manually verified the translation of each of more than 600 unique species codes used in the various source inventories. We also resolved some problems in the use of the biophysical inventory data for Wood Buffalo National Park allowing us to correctly integrate this critical area into our national avian habitat models. Finding, testing and correcting these errors took up almost three person-months of programmer and GIS analyst time, and more than three weeks of Cumming's time, which explains some of the delay of the application of the CASFRI data to bird habitat models. As of March 2013, the corrected dataset is being used to build bird-habitat models for certain species (See Section 2.2.1).

2.2 Population Estimation and Projection through Space and Time

2.2.1 National scale bird-habitat models using Forest Resource Inventory data

The size of the boreal bird populations depends on the amount and availability of suitable breeding habitats. Habitat suitability at large spatial scales is often modeled using different land cover classification schemes. Suitability can vary greatly within the same habitat class due to disturbance events (fire, insect outbreaks, human activity, etc.) and the age of the habitat (time since last disturbance).

We used the BAM avian point count database (Version 3, February 2013) combined with the CASFRI biophysical dataset to develop boreal-wide predictive models for boreal birds. The CASFRI integrates Forest Resource Inventories (FRIs) from across Canada into a common attribute schema (CAS). These data allowed us to define consistent habitat classification and forest age variables within the study area covered by the CASFRI in Canada. The CASFRI product should represent an improvement over satellite-derived layers such as LCC05 used in the BAM density estimates currently available on our website due to improved resolution of habitat type and stand age.

We derived a procedure that translates CASFRI information into habitat classes (deciduous forest, mixedwood, upland conifer, lowland conifer, shrubs, grassland, wetland, cultivation, urban/industrial areas) and age information for forested habitats. Habitat types using point intersection was based on tree species composition for forested patches, and CASFRI types for non-forested areas (as documented in the [online standards manual](#)). Wetness information was also used to define wetland habitats and also to differentiate between upland and lowland coniferous forests. Point counts predating year of origin were excluded from analysis.

For habitat association models, we used Poisson generalized linear models (GLM) with log link. We used 200 bootstrap runs to account for uneven spatial sampling within the study area. Bootstrap was combined with variable selection based on information criteria measures (AIC, BIC). We weighted survey visits by the inverse square root of the number of visits in 4 x 4 km grid cells to account for the non-independence (clustered nature) of the data set. We used recently developed correction factors (Sólymos et al. 2012b) to account for differences in sampling protocol and nuisance parameters affecting detectability.

We then built habitat association models including habitat classes (deciduous forest, mixedwood, upland conifer, lowland conifer, shrubs, grassland, wetland, cultivation, urban/industrial areas), and linear and quadratic age relationships. We also allowed the age relationship to vary among forest types through interaction effects, and assumed no age relationship in open habitats.

We conducted preliminary tests of differential habitat selection via comparison of species habitat associations in the western vs. the eastern half of the country. The Ontario-Manitoba border was used as the divide between eastern and western Canada. Differential habitat selection means that the ranking of different habitats based on relative habitat suitability is a function of spatial location. Differential habitat selection was tested by interaction terms between model parameters for

habitat/age and spatial location (east-west). An interaction term supported by multi-model inference (bootstrap aggregation) was interpreted as a sign for differential habitat selection. Regional (Alberta) models for Canada Warbler are discussed in Section 2.4.

2.2.2 Variation in species density and habitat selection between the eastern and western boreal forest

The purpose of the modelling exercise was to develop a model-based methodology to determine whether species exhibit a detectable geographic variation in habitat selection at national scales. In these initial explorations, we tested for regional differences between the eastern and western boreal regions, using the Ontario-Manitoba border as the divide. We developed models for three species of conservation interest: Canada Warbler (CAWA); Connecticut Warbler (CONW); and Black-throated Green Warbler (BTNW). We will further develop our models based on this work to extend to the full suite of boreal species for which we have appropriate data, as well as exploring the ecological and management implications of these results.

We deliberately provided a simplistic description of spatial variation of abundance (east vs. west) to allow us to test regionally-different habitat selection. An alternative way could be to include spatial covariates, especially climate, into the models. A large number of covariates would make testing for differential habitat selection more difficult. This might, however, be important for spatial prediction and scenario analysis. We provide initial results as proof-of-concept, and we will pursue the modelling and scenario analysis further based on feedback from the Technical Committee (see 2.2.2.5).

2.2.2.1 Canada Warbler (national scale)

Based on the national habitat association models created for Canada Warbler, we found that Canada Warbler density was highest in deciduous and mixedwood stands, and in wetlands (Figure 2). Canada Warbler density was low in coniferous stands. There was no difference between densities predicted for upland and lowland (bogs) coniferous forest. Canada Warbler density was also low in shrub and grassland habitats, and in cultivated and urban/industrial areas. There was a strong age relationship within deciduous stands, as density increased with age. However, the age relationship was not significant in non-deciduous stands. The east-west difference was best described by an additive term which indicates differences in density in the different areas of the country. However, spatial interactions were not significant indicating that the data and models did not support the differential habitat selection hypothesis for Canada Warbler. Therefore, no large differences in densities were detected across the range of Canada Warbler.

Figure 2: Expected Canada Warbler density as the function of habitat type (A-C) and forest type and forest age (D-F). Top graphs (A, D) show results from national models with no spatial differences assumed. Bottom plots show the expected density west (B, E) and east (C, F) of the Ontario-Manitoba border. Forest habitat types in A-C represent 80 years old stands (see corresponding grey vertical line in D-F).

2.2.2.2 Connecticut Warbler (national scale)

Based on the national habitat association models we created for Connecticut Warbler (CONW), we found that Connecticut Warbler density was highest in deciduous stands, moderate in shrubs,

grasslands, wetlands, and urban/industrial areas (Figure 3). Connecticut Warbler density was low in non-deciduous forests, and expected density was zero in cultivated areas. There was a strong age relationship within deciduous stands; density peaked at 70 years of age. The east-west difference was not very pronounced. The highest density for forest age shifted from 70 years in the west to 80 years in the east, and expected density in old growth forests (>100 years) was higher in the east than in the west in all four forest types. Contrary to small differences in relative habitat selection, there was large, almost three-fold, difference between the eastern and western absolute densities. The pattern with higher density in western areas is similar to the density pattern we found based on spatial density models currently posted on BAM website and based on LCC05 vegetation cover.

Figure 3: Expected Connecticut Warbler density as the function of habitat type (A-C) and forest type and forest age (D-F). Top graphs (A, D) show results from national models with no spatial differences assumed. Bottom plots show the expected density west (B, E) and east (C, F) of the Ontario-Manitoba border. Forest habitat types in A-C represent 80 years old stands (see corresponding grey vertical line in D-F).

2.2.2.3 Black Throated Green Warbler (national level)

The national habitat association models for Black-throated Green Warbler showed that Black-throated Green Warbler density was consistently higher in forest habitats. Expected density was intermediate in wetlands and low in open and disturbed habitats. There was a strong age relationship and density peaked at 70 years of age for mixedwood and coniferous stands, while the density was highest in old growth deciduous forests (Figure 4). The east-west difference was pronounced for deciduous forests. The highest density for deciduous forest age shifted from 100-150 years in the west to 90 years in the east. The difference between age relationships in deciduous forests and in other forest types was markedly more pronounced in the west than in the east. There was some difference between the eastern and western absolute densities. Density in forest habitats was consistently higher in the eastern areas than in the west. This density pattern is similar to what we found based on spatial density models currently posted on BAM website and based on LCC05 vegetation cover.

Figure 4: Expected Black-throated Green Warbler density as the function of habitat type (A-C) and forest type and forest age (D-F). Top graphs (A, D) show results from national models with no spatial differences assumed. Bottom plots show the expected density west (B, E) and east (C, F) of the Ontario-Manitoba border. Forest habitat types in A-C represent 80 years old stands (see corresponding grey vertical line in D-F).

2.2.3 Development of national habitat models for use in Scenario Evaluation

2.2.3.1 Forest management activities: incorporation into Tardis

As we have described in previous BAM progress reports, Tardis is a suite of methods and software for low spatial resolution simulation over very large areas, targeted at forest management and natural disturbances in the boreal forest. Tardis is a grid-based model. The current version uses the 300 arc second grid used by Natural Resources Canada to interpolate climate surfaces (McKenney et al. 2006); climate change scenarios can also be downscaled to this grid. Thus, Tardis can conveniently be linked to present and projected future climate surfaces. Model cells are approximately 100 km² in southern Canada, a very small size in a national context. The current version of Tardis is initialised from the CASFRI inventory. Every model cell keeps track of the areas, age structure and species compositions of forested patches, and the total area of various non-forested types. The use of CASFRI data allows the model to integrate forest management and avian habitat models such as presented in the previous section.

The following has been accomplished:

- A library of spatially-referenced stand volume-age models has been assembled for every jurisdiction in boreal region of Canada, except BC and the Maritime Provinces, and has been processed into a standard format. The assistance of a regional forestry expert is needed to develop tables for BC. The Maritime Provinces are only partially integrated into the Tardis framework. An amendment to the Contribution Agreement in 2011-2012 provided funds to incorporate FRI data from the region into the CASFRI product, and this was done as previously reported. However, it has not yet been possible to assemble other forest management data for the hemiboreal region, including mill locations, capacities, operating areas and stand volume-age tables. These tables are essential for linking the avian habitat models to the FRI data. Thus for the moment, we use tables from adjacent regions to cover southern Québec and the Maritimes. All tables are fully linked to the Tardis harvesting and ecological models. A method of automatically assigning tables to FRI polygons has been developed that takes account of stand age and species composition, as well as site index, stand density or soil moisture regime where known.
- The total wood supply for each large forest products mill has been disaggregated and spatially referenced to specific geographic regions (Forest Management Units or Forest Management Agreement Areas; see Figure 5). This task was completed for Ontario in May 2012.
- Preliminary national simulations of the Tardis harvest model were presented at the NAOC meeting in August 2012.

A report documenting the sources and processing methods for all these forestry data sets was completed in March 2013 (in French). It will be posted on the BAM website in 2013-14. The underlying shapefiles and data tables have been assembled into a library that echoes the structure of the report and the Tardis input data files. Most of the spatial data can be made available on request; only some detailed records of provincial allocations are confidential. Access to the provincial stand age tables would require

revisiting permissions with the donor agencies.

The Tardis model is now capable of simulating forest harvesting over all of Canada, with caveats noted above. An indication of the model's spatial extent and the capacity to simulate forest management capacity is shown in Figure 5. The map shows the ratio of total allocation to forest products firms divided by an estimate of Annual Allowable Cut calculated from forest stand volume-age tables and Forest Resource Inventory data. The model had to integrate all the forestry input data mentioned above to map the proportional allocation of forest wood and fibre productivity in boreal Canada. The effects of recent mill-closures in eastern Manitoba, central Saskatchewan and northeast BC are apparent. No significant mill capacity exists currently in the YT or NT. The enormous spatial variation in the intensity of forest resource allocation has potentially large effects on optimal conservation plans.

Figure 5: Proportional allocation of Canada's forest resource to forest products mills, calculated for each Forest Management Unit. Forest management data were not available for the hemiboreal regions of BC and QC, or for the Maritime Provinces.

2.2.3.2 Fire model

The capacity to simulate lightning fire regime was re-implemented in Tardis in March 2013. Spatial variation in three fire regime parameters (the frequency of large fires, and two parameters defining the fire size distribution) were mapped by Cumming at a spatial resolution of 10,000 km², using data from the Canadian Large Fire Database. These large scale maps were downscaled to the Tardis grid, and provided as input parameter maps. The fire model code was revised to remove boreal-mixedwood

specific models of the relation between forest cover type and fire behaviour, and many bugs attendant on expanding the spatial extent of the simulation by a factor of 100 were corrected. Tardis now replicates the main effects of fire on the boreal forest (e.g., Figure 6), that is to say the spatial patterning of age-class structures. This integrates, for the first time, the interactions between natural disturbance regimes, forest management and conservation planning at national extents. Ongoing fire research in Cumming’s lab and elsewhere will allow us to include other fire-related processes in this framework, such as: human-caused fires; fire suppression, which is needed for estimating the natural range of variation in model outputs; and fire-climate interactions that could be used for long-range forecasting of changes in fire regime to be expected under climate change. These features would allow Tardis to better forecast the trends and variability in future forest conditions and thus in the distribution and abundances of forest songbirds. The fire research itself is outside the scope of BAM.

Figure 6. Simulation of area burned in Ontario over one 5yr model time step (Year 2015-2020). The spatial variation in fire regime is evident, with fire more common in the northwestern region.

2.2.3.3 Protected Areas specification

A flexible system of representing permanent or temporary protected areas has been implemented in Tardis. Protected areas can be specified at the level of Tardis cells, or at the level of individual FRI polygons. The method has been tested on the existing protected areas network. Shapefiles of all IUCN-recognised protected areas in Canada were obtained from the Canadian Council of Ecological Areas website. These were intersected with the FRI coverage to identify all protected polygons based on the locations of their centroids. Tardis can allow harvesting in these areas or not, and can calculate the Annual Allowable Cut removed from commercial exploitation by these areas. This economic cost can be evaluated against the numbers of different bird species protected. Methods for incorporating protected areas designated by the Canadian BEACONS project have been designed, but not yet fully tested.

2.2.3.4 Methods to implement national habitat models in Tardis

From December 2012 through March 2013, we designed and implemented a very general method that allows for the spatial and temporal projection in Tardis of avian habitat models such as reported in Section 2.2.1. The details are technical, but involve a standard classification based on FRI attributes, an agreed set of covariates and 1st and 2nd order interaction terms, a link function, and a way of aggregating polygon level predictions up to a 300 arc-second model cell. The method has been tested using the three preliminary national FRI models reported in Section 2.2.1, namely Canada Warbler (CAWA), Connecticut Warbler (CONW) and Black-throated Green Warbler (BTNW). This represents the first projection of FRI-based avian habitat models at a national extent.

Note that the models projected in the Figure7 were developed to test for east-west gradients in habitat selection based on stand-level FRI attributes only. The model does not directly include effects of climate which are known to be important. Therefore, latitudinal and longitudinal gradients represent patterns of relative abundances of forested and non-forested habitats and the species-composition and age-class structure of forested stands. Neither vegetation nor climate necessarily determined bird avian distributions alone, because trees and birds have different physiological tolerances. Birds might be excluded from areas that are climatically suitable for lack of required vegetation types, and be absent from patches of preferred forest type because of unfavourable climate. Until avian models are developed that are designed for spatial prediction, and that include both factors, maps such as these should be interpreted as proofs-of-concept. BAM will be developing such models during 2013-2014.

Figure 7: An implementation in Tardis of the first national habitat model, of the Canada Warbler, developed using FRI data as reported in section 2.2.1. See the text for cautions against over-interpretation.

2.2.3.5 National Scenario Analysis of future impacts of forest harvesting

As proposed in our contribution agreement, we started using national models based on the CASFRI data in conjunction with Tardis simulation experiments to project avian species abundances spatially and through time. The initial design considers two factors: conditions of forest management (harvesting or no harvesting); and protected areas (maintained as protected, or considered available for harvesting). The conditions of natural disturbance (fire sub-model) would be enabled in all cases. We track the total abundance of selected birds over time, and the available harvest volumes. All indicators are stratified between protected areas and commercial forests.

Initial trial scenarios were run in 2013 for three species (CAWA, CONW, and BTNW), as tests. A single model run of 150 years (30 model time-steps) was performed for each scenario. Each simulation took 70 minutes which represents a very significant increase in performance relative to earlier versions of the model. This is largely due to exhaustive code optimization by the lead programmer, Dr. Benedicte Kenmei. With these speeds, Monte-Carlo simulation trials of 100 runs for each of multiple scenarios are feasible. The most cost effective approach for further increases in efficiency would be to purchase one or more additional servers, or lease capacity from a cloud-based provider.

The critical steps before further scenario development are creating species distribution models designed for projection in Tardis that account for climatic constraints on species distributions and for the main effects of forest harvesting and human land use (see description of CASFRI national habitat models above). In particular, statistical models should include covariates for landscape-scale effects, such as proportion of favorable habitat or disturbances measured within cells. It is our intention to address this material in time for presentation to the International Boreal Forest Research Association (IBFRA) meeting in October 2013.

We had planned on engaging members of the Technical Committee to help design the scenario analyses, including specifications of the indicators to be reported. However, initial focus on simulation details did not present an effective use of this capacity. Instead, we propose to work with interested Technical Committee members over the next six months, perhaps using a dedicated workshop format to develop a new suite of models suited for national scenario analyses. We will also integrate this modelling approach with the initiatives to model landscape effects on habitat quality, and to incorporate and contribute to other national initiatives, notably the conservation planning work of the Canadian Boreal Forest Agreement.

2.2.4 Climate Change

Global climate models project the rapid warming of boreal and arctic regions of North America (Ruckstuhl et al. 2008). This has led to predictions that boreal forest vegetation and fauna will track these changes and shift northward into the arctic over the next century. We used BAM's comprehensive dataset of avian point-count surveys from across boreal Canada and Alaska, combined with interpolated climate data, to develop bioclimatic niche models of current avian distribution and density for 102 native songbird species (74 boreal species). We then used a downscaling of projected climates in future periods (2011–2040, 2041–2070, 2071–2100) to assess the potential for these species to shift their ranges and change their abundance across North America's boreal region in response to climate change.

We used our models to project changes in potential abundance, map projected shifts in distribution and density, and identify potential climate "refugia": areas that are projected to maintain suitable climates for breeding in both current and future periods. On average across 11 model runs, 34 of the 74 boreal songbird species evaluated were projected to decline in potential abundance by 2100 based on mean projections of future climate change across the boreal and southern arctic region (Appendix Tables 4 and 5). By the end of the century, the species with the largest projected decreases across the boreal and southern arctic regions were American Tree Sparrow (-93%), White-crowned Sparrow (-88%), and Common Redpoll (-87%). Sixty-eight species (40 boreal) were projected to increase in abundance by 2100, including the brood parasite Brown-headed Cowbird and avian nest predators American Crow and Blue Jay.

According to model projections, conservation responsibilities would shift geographically, with many boreal species projected to decline in BCRs 6 and 8 while increasing in BCRs 4 and 7 (Appendix Table 6). Within BCR 4 (Northwestern Interior Forest), 21 species were projected to decline in abundance by the end of the century, the largest percentage declines being projected for Common Redpoll (-89%), Gray-cheeked Thrush (-87%), and White-crowned Sparrow (-86%). The largest percentage increases were

projected for Black-throated Green Warbler, Ovenbird, and Red-eyed Vireo. Within BCR 6 (Boreal Taiga Plains), 53 species were projected to decline by 2100, of which the top three were American Tree Sparrow (-96%), White-crowned Sparrow (-92%), and Gray-cheeked Thrush (-88%). Other notable projected declines were for Connecticut Warbler (-83%), Tennessee Warbler (-77%), and Yellow-rumped Warbler (-69%). The top three projected increasing species in BCR 6 were Red-winged Blackbird, Pine Warbler, and Vesper Sparrow. Within BCR 7 (Taiga Shield and Hudson Plain), 25 species were projected to decline in abundance, with American Pipit (-77%) and Rusty Blackbird (-72%) ranking among the top declining species. Black-throated Green Warbler, American Redstart, and Chestnut-sided Warbler were the species with the largest projected increases in BCR 7. Finally, 41 species within BCR 8 (Boreal Softwood Shield), including Gray Jay (-88%) and White-winged Crossbill (-83%) were projected to decline in abundance by 2100. Great-crested Flycatcher, Indigo Bunting, and Scarlet Tanager had the highest projected percent increases in BCR 8 by the end of the century.

Models revealed the potential for dramatic northward shifts in suitable climates for boreal-nesting songbirds based on projections of climate change over the next century (Appendix Figures 2-3). If these changes in climate are accompanied by rapid northward shifts in boreal forest vegetation, then our models imply large shifts in avian distribution and abundance from the boreal forest region into the southern arctic region for a wide range of species, with declines in abundance projected for many species. If a more likely scenario prevails whereby changes in boreal vegetation do not keep pace with the rapid northward shift in suitable climates, then climate-change refugia will be particularly important for birds, with the proportion of species' core ranges maintained as refugia likely linked to the species' abilities to maintain its population sizes through time. However, our models indicate that an average of only 45% of current core areas across 74 boreal species is likely to persist in climate-change refugia by the end of the century, with 16 species retaining $\leq 10\%$ of their core ranges (Appendix Table 7, Figure 4). Large losses of core area may result in population declines unless the distributional losses are mitigated by increases in breeding density within the current core range.

For two species of conservation concern, Olive-sided Flycatcher and Rusty Blackbird, our models projected that suitable climatic conditions for breeding will become more restricted and fragmented in the future, and that only a small portion of the current ranges of these species will exist in climate-change refugia by the end of the century (Figure 8). This has the potential to exacerbate the already steep population declines of these species. For a third species of conservation concern, Canada Warbler, models projected an increase in potential abundance of more than 50%, although refugia by 2100 would comprise just half of its current core distribution (Figure 8).

Several broad-scale biogeographic patterns were also apparent from model projections (Appendix Figures 2-3). First, many boreal species, especially the eastern wood warblers such as Black-throated Green and Cape May Warbler were projected to expand northwestward across western mountain ranges into Alaska (BCR 4). In most cases suitable climatic conditions already exist in Alaska but would become connected with boreal Canada over time. Second, for several boreal specialist species such as Boreal Chickadee and Bay-breasted Warbler, future climatic conditions were projected to result in the splitting of currently contiguous ranges, resulting in distinct eastern and western ranges separated by Hudson Bay (mostly within BCR 7). Finally, for boreal mixedwood species such as Ovenbird and

Mourning Warbler, projected range loss and fragmentation was more pronounced in the west (BCR 6) compared to the east (BCR 8).

A technical report addressing this topic is attached as an appendix. Limited distribution is requested until scientific manuscripts (currently in preparation) are submitted for publication. The first manuscript on quantifying sources of prediction uncertainty is estimated to be completed by June 2013. The second manuscript on identifying multi-species conservation priorities based on climate-change refugia is expected to be completed by September 2013.

Figure 8 : Mean projected climate-change refugia for Canada Warbler (CAWA), Olive-sided Flycatcher (OSFL), and Rusty Blackbird (RUBL) based on climate-only density models. Refugia (dark green) are areas that maintain \geq average breeding densities (core areas) between the baseline period of 1961–1990 and each future time period (A, B, C). Areas in gold represent baseline core areas lost, light green represent future core areas gained, and areas in grey represent below average densities in baseline and future periods. Boreal and southern arctic regions are divided by the red line.

2.2.5 Sampling Methodology

BAM team members have been preparing manuscripts to describe the methodological advances we have developed to address the complexities of the extensive BAM database and improved estimates of density. Publication through the peer-review journals will ensure credibility of these novel analytical approaches and flow as a logical final step to analyses supported under previous contribution agreements.

In Sólymos et al. (“Calibrating indices”) we describe BAM’s reformulation of removal and distance sampling models to adjust the raw counts from point-count surveys for the effects of survey protocol and temporal and environmental covariates (e.g., time, date, habitat type) on detection probabilities. We show that survey protocol is a large source of variation in detection probabilities. Further, our combination of models is effective in controlling for this effect and producing estimates of avian breeding density that are robust to variation in survey protocol. A revision of this paper was submitted to *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* in April 2013.

In Sólymos et al. (“Using a removal model”) we evaluate the accuracy and precision associated with using removal models to adjust point-count surveys for variation in length of the counting time. We evaluate two forms of the removal model: (1) a simple exponential model where singing rates are assumed to be homogeneous in the population, and (2) a two-point mixture model that accommodates birds with low and high singing rates. We also explore sample size requirements for these models. We are currently revising this paper and plan to resubmit it to the *Auk* in June 2013.

We are currently developing a paper by Matsuoka et al. (“Roadside bias in point-count surveys”) in which we report an 80% prevalence in roadside bias in the counts across 80 species of boreal forest songbirds, with the prevalence and magnitude of positive roadside bias twice that of negative roadside bias. This will influence how BBS data (collected on roadsides) can be used in our habitat models, as roadside sampling may result in overestimation of population densities for most species. We also evaluate whether this roadside bias in the counts can be controlled using road width, detection distance to birds, differences in affinity of birds to edges, or the subtraction of habitat by the road corridor.

2.2.5.1 Scoping exercise on errors in Forest Resource Inventory Data

The models described in Section 2.2.2 used forest age as a covariate. Forest age in CASFRI data is subject to error; this means its value is not known with certainty. We performed a scoping exercise to formalize the processes that are responsible for the measurement error in age. This will allow us to create model-based solutions for the problem, and contrast it with our current approach of ignoring the measurement error in forest age when using generalized linear models (GLM).

The error associated with the age estimates is influenced by many factors. Forest height is measured, and age is inferred based on height. This might imply that height is quite reliably measured in the year of photography. Inferred age based on height-age relationship is known to be more reliable for younger/smaller stands than for old stands where height growth declines and total height levels off after a certain age. But more-or-less sudden changes in canopy structure, such as canopy collapse, can occur in some kinds of old stands, and these changes can also contribute to age errors.

We identified two processes that eventually contribute to the overall measurement error: 1) unknown processes affecting mostly older age classes (e.g. canopy collapse); 2) systematic error related to the accuracy of the height-age conversion. The first process might be described as a threshold effect, i.e. error is negligible below and constant above the age threshold. The second process might be described by a variance function exponential in the mean. The two processes combined would produce a sigmoid-shaped variance function with age that can be described by logistic or Gompertz growth curves. The shape (parameters) of the curve would make it possible to describe the relative contribution of the two processes.

This measurement error model applies when age is exact. In the FRI data, however, year of origin is registered by lower and upper bounds. Sometimes the two bounds match, sometimes they don't. It is called interval-censored data when only the range of a quantity is known. Sometimes only the upper bound for year of origin is known (left censored). The age is the difference between true year of origin and known year of sampling.

Accounting for measurement error in FRI data is a multilevel modelling problem (age, censored year of origin, measurement error in inferred year of origin). Such models are problematic to work with. First, no packaged software can fit such models to the data so we need to create an estimating procedure. Second, the size of the dataset would require code optimization to make the computations at the FRI scale feasible; therefore we need to devise algorithms where convergence is fast and accurate (compiled code for Hamiltonian Monte Carlo simulations).

Other sources of error in the FRI data arise from the time interval between year of aerial photography and year of bird survey. Some aspects of this (stand gaining, height growth) can be accounted for fairly simply in terms of elapsed time. However, disturbances such as fire and harvesting that occur in the interval between the two measurements are more difficult to handle. In most provinces, some form of periodic updates for inventories (depletion allowances) are available, which in CASFRI are represented as disturbance records. Any further development of the CASFRI dataset will need to focus on better describing disturbance histories in relation to avian sampling history.

2.3 Informing monitoring needs and strategies for landbirds

2.3.1 Standardised data for evaluation of monitoring designs for proposed National Wildlife Areas in NWT

Environment Canada used portions of BAM's dataset (including BBS data and existing EC studies) to assist with evaluation of monitoring program design for songbirds in four proposed National Wildlife Areas in the NWT. An analysis was conducted to predict the precision of trends that would result from designs with differing sampling intensities and duration. BAM provided standardized data in a consolidated format that permitted utilisation of multiple data sources into this analysis. Results showed a strong effect of program duration (number of years) as well as re-visit schedule (1 vs 5 years) as well as lesser effects of number of sites. Local abundance of species also had an effect on precision. Detailed results are presented [in a technical report that is posted to the BAM website](#).

2.3.2 Data and support for predictive bird-habitat models for Joint Oil Sands Monitoring

BAM is providing scientific support and access to its database to support development of bird-habitat models that will be used in the Effects Assessment component of the Joint Oil Sands Monitoring (JOSM) program. This component will focus on (1) conducting point count surveys to fill data gaps across representative habitat types within the oil sands area of Alberta, and (2) developing empirical bird-habitat models to assess changes in population size using habitat change and land use scenario analyses. BAM and EC worked collaboratively to develop standardized point count protocols to ensure consistent data collection and integration of new data with existing data sources for use in bird-habitat modelling and population estimation. BAM provided the spatial locations of all existing point counts within the oil sands area of Alberta to assess the representation of point counts across habitat types and guide the development of an extensive stratified sampling plan for 2013 (>4500 point count locations within 41 habitat types across 11 geographic locations in northeast and north-central Alberta). These data will fill current data gaps within all representative habitat types in the oil sands area of Alberta. BAM and EC are working collaboratively to develop the products and approaches required to create bird-habitat models that will be used to predict how habitat change from oil sands activities and other resource activities influences both habitat supply and population size estimates for boreal birds. In particular, BAM and EC analysts and scientists are working to: define, create, and manage shared habitat and human footprint data layers; develop approaches to extract and summarise habitat and human footprint data at multiple scales; develop analytical approaches (e.g. appropriate spatial scale, relevant covariates, model structure, model selection, model evaluation) for modelling and validating predictive bird-habitat models; and utilise current BAM products to adjust predicted count estimates to density estimates to generate population size estimates.

2.3.3 Protocol recommendations on BAM website

Recommendations for conducting point count protocols are posted on our website at http://www.borealbirds.ca/index.php/data_collection_guidance. These recommendations are designed to generate datasets that allow the greatest flexibility in analysing results, especially in permitting the use of more complex forms of removal or time-of-detection models as well as distance sampling. As ongoing work suggests new protocols for avian monitoring protocols, they will be added to the website. BAM recommendations for conducting point counts were incorporated into the 2012 field sampling protocols for the Effects Assessment component of the Joint Oil Sands Monitoring (JOSM) program. Standardised point count protocols will be used to conduct extensive field sampling in 2013 to fill data gaps within all representative habitat types in the oil sands area of Alberta. Using standardised protocols ensures that new data can be combined with all existing data sources to model bird-habitat relationships, adjust count estimates to density estimates, and assess the current and future effects of habitat change on population size estimates within the oil sands area.

A manuscript titled “There and back again? Revisiting common standards for conducting point-count surveys to estimate breeding abundance of terrestrial birds in northern North America” was submitted to *Auk*, and was rejected in February 2013. We are currently revising it to address issues of length and

focus of the article. The reviewer comments are being considered by the team to see how best they might be addressed, and if resubmission is warranted, it could occur in September 2013.

2.3.4. Impact of Sound Transmission on Point Counts

In conjunction with field work being conducted by the Bayne laboratory, we compared the properties of sound transmission perpendicular to versus parallel to low-use forestry roads to validate the assumption that differences in bird counts between forest interior and road-side locations reflect actual differences in bird abundance, and not just the increased ability to hear sounds along a roadway. A playback-recording experiment was designed to broadcast sounds perpendicular and parallel to roadways to see if sound propagation differed in the two directions. We found no differences in the probability of detection, signal-to-noise ratio, or attenuation rates parallel versus perpendicular to low-use forestry roads. Major differences were found in the distance over which sounds with different frequencies and amplitude could be detected, but the pattern was consistent between transects parallel and perpendicular to the road. Our results suggest that differences in bird counts between on- and off-road point counts are not likely caused by differences in sound transmission on the width and types of roads sampled. The variation in distance over which sounds can be heard between forest types has significant implications for estimation of density, particularly from recorders, in different forest types. A manuscript is currently under review with the Journal of Field Ornithology.

2.4 Conservation planning: National and Regional Projects

2.4.1. Regional Distribution of Canada Warbler in Alberta

Our goal was to relate the distribution and abundance of a mature-forest specialist, the Canada Warbler (a Threatened species under SAR), to habitat and landscape variables in Alberta in a spatially-explicit manner. Numbers of Canada Warbler have declined across their range, including Alberta where habitat loss and habitat alteration from agriculture, urban expansion and industrial development are rapidly changing the forest landscape. This work was conducted in partnership with the Government of Alberta and through additional support of EC's Habitat Stewardship Program. The quantity of point count data in Alberta as well as detailed biophysical data layers available at the provincial scale allowed us to pursue detailed, spatially explicit models of density and distribution appropriate for application in land use planning and environmental impacts assessment at regional scales. Approaches applied here will be applicable in other jurisdictions where sufficient data exist.

We used 43,927 point count survey visits from the BAM and ABMI datasets as well as a directed field study in 2012 to model the habitat associations of Canada Warblers at local (150 m) and landscape (451 m) scales. We found that suitable Canada Warbler habitat was broadly distributed across Alberta's boreal region with a general increase in suitability from west to east and from south to north. Local concentrations of suitable habitat were associated with old growth deciduous forests, particularly near small, incised streams at the local scale, and a deciduous forest matrix at the landscape scale (Figure 9). A manuscript addressing this research is in preparation.

Figure 9 Predictive map of expected Canada Warbler density in Alberta. Values were based on 200 bootstrap iterations; the mapping unit is one quarter section area (0.64 km²).

2.4.2 Canada Warbler: Opportunities for mitigation of habitat loss at regional scales

The focus of our Canada Warbler project in Alberta was to identify their habitat requirements and to determine best management practices for their conservation. Our results clearly demonstrate that the largest proportion of Alberta's Canada Warbler population is found in older forests near streams. Current operating rules for Alberta's forestry companies protect, to some degree, the habitat of the Canada Warbler but more information is needed on whether the buffers created for stream protection are sufficient to support Canada Warbler populations in the long-term. The retention of residual tree patches and understory protection measures during harvesting also will benefit the Canada Warbler. Ensuring that harvest blocks are not sprayed with herbicides to prevent shrub growth is also important as those Canada Warbler found in early seral habitat are always associated with a dense shrub understory.

While best management practices may reduce the effects of forestry on Canada Warbler, it remains to be seen whether such practices will be sufficient to ensure the species' persistence in the future. A key step in developing recovery plans for Canada Warbler will be to evaluate how harvest management plans will affect Canada Warbler habitat supply into the future. The model we created is being distributed to forestry companies across Alberta to allow them to compute how their management plans will influence Canada Warbler numbers into the future. BAM is also conducting simulations. In April 2013, Bayne will present this model and others created by BAM to forestry practitioners at the College of Alberta Professional Forest Technologists. This forum will allow us to interact with all of the forestry companies in Alberta and show them how to apply the Canada Warbler model and other BAM tools for more informed forest management.

While individual companies will assess the risk to Canada Warbler posed by their forest management plans, the efficacy of their mitigation efforts may be insufficient to protect Canada Warbler without other intervention. A complementary strategy is to identify areas where habitat protection might be achieved. In the Lower and Upper Peace land use zones in Alberta, we found that 8.8% of the Canada Warbler population is protected within existing parks or conservation lands based on the density model described above. We used the Canada Warbler map to determine how best to build a reserve network from this protected areas network that would protect 30% of the Canada Warbler population. The program MARXAN was used to create hypothetical protected areas networks. The 30% protection criterion was arbitrary, and any level could be evaluated if there are other objectives. In this particular application we only considered "land area" as the cost and thus tried to minimize the area and perimeter of the reserve network that would have to be purchased to achieve our objective. Figure 10 and 11 show the best solutions required to protect 30% of the Canada Warbler population in the Upper and Lower Peace region. Figure 10 shows the frequency out of 100 runs that each section was selected by Marxan as being needed to achieve this objective. Figure 11 shows the optimal proposed protected areas that would achieve 30% protection. The average size of the reserve network required to achieve this 30% protection objective would be about 20,000 km² in addition to existing parks and lands managed by the Alberta Conservation Association for wildlife protection.

This planning model is fairly basic and needs further development to take into account numerous economic and ecological issues before specific protected areas could be recommended. We looked at the Lower and Upper Peace planning regions specifically as the value of this land is generally for agriculture or forestry. The economics of purchasing such land is relatively straightforward and thus it would be more plausible that the province of Alberta or other parties might consider protection for these areas. Other areas of the province (e.g. oilsands in the east) have significantly greater economic value and thus are not “equal” from a socio-economic perspective and, in the case of the Canada Warbler, are not equal ecologically (more Canada Warbler are found in the west). In addition, areas within the oilsands have relatively little protected areas from which to begin building a protected areas network.

The Marxan model takes into account current composition of the forest, age structure, and current human footprint. However, it does not actively change these into the future to see what the value of these areas would be over the longer term. All protected areas should be viewed as dynamic in that natural processes (i.e. fire) can rapidly alter forest age structure and composition in both protected and non-protected areas. This means that the value of these protected areas as conservation tools for Canada Warbler will change in the future. This is an area BAM plans to investigate over the coming year.

Figure 10: Best Solution from Marxan modelling for protection of 30% of Canada Warbler range in Upper and Lower Peace Planning Regions of Alberta. Selection frequency refers to outcomes of a model run. The polygons shown represent the landuse framework regions of Alberta. The model was created for the Upper and Lower Peace regions which are the NW corner and the area directly south.

Figure 11: Highest Frequency solution from Marxan modelling for protection of 30% of Canada Warbler range within the Upper and Lower Peace Planning Regions of Alberta. The polygons shown represent the landuse framework regions of Alberta. The model was created for the Upper and Lower Peace regions which are the NW corner and the area directly south.

2.4.3 Use of BAM data to test validity of biodiversity surrogates: BEACONS partnership

Most systematic conservation planning methodologies are based on ideas of ecological representation, where representation is measured with respect to biodiversity surrogates. “Surrogates” are variables such as climate or remote-sensed land-cover or other factors relatively easy to measure and map that are expected to be correlated with species’ abundances or other aspects of biodiversity that are not directly measured. The assumption is that the more closely a protected areas design captures the variation of the surrogates within a planning region (e.g. a BCR), the better the job it will do in protecting all components of regional biodiversity, including all those not directly measured. BAM’s capacity to develop predictive species abundance models for a large number of avian species offers a rare chance to test this cornerstone supposition of systematic conservation planning.

The Canadian BEACONS Project has developed a novel approach to systematic conservation planning in the boreal region. Like many such approaches, it is based on a carefully chosen suite of environmental surrogates, in this case: 1) the Canada Land Cover 2005 map; 2) an eight-year mean of annual gross primary productivity (GPP) measured by satellite imagery (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer, MODIS); 3) a climate- and insolation-based measure of soil moisture; and 4) a measure of the abundance of riparian habitat developed from hydrological maps. One novel feature of the BEACONS approach is the use of multivariate distance metrics based on the dissimilarity of distributions of surrogates between a candidate protected area and a planning region. BEACONS designs for candidate protected areas networks seek to minimize this distance. Designs where the distance is small should be better at conserving biodiversity than designs where the distance is large. We developed a new method to test this supposition.

Consider a protected area that covers 10% of a planning region. It will not likely accommodate 10% of the abundance of all species present, because species’ spatial distributions and densities are not all the same; some species increase and others decrease in abundance with latitude, for example. We hypothesized that a good protected areas design would represent a tradeoff between the mean and variance of the proportion of species’ ranges or abundances that occurred within it. The mean should be as high as possible, and the variance as low as possible. This led to a further hypothesis: *if* BEACONS choice of environmental surrogates was good *then* the variance among species in the proportional abundance protected by a network *should be* inversely proportional to the network’s distance metric. We tested this hypothesis using predictive species abundance models for about 90 species of forest songbirds, developed by BAM (Diana Stralberg) and reported in the 2009-2012 BAM report. Working with BEACONS team member Pierre Vernier, we evaluated a large sample of protected areas designs for four large regions in Canada (defined by ocean drainages) at protection targets of 20, 30 and 40% of area. For each region and target, we generated 100,000 random network designs. For each network, we calculated the distance metric and the variance over the 90 species in the proportional species’ abundance. The results (Figure 12) strongly supported the hypothesis. As the multivariate distance metric decreased, the variance (expressed as a standard deviation) declined as well. Similar results were found for all four planning regions at all target levels. This confirms that the BEACONS surrogates are valid planning tools for preserving biodiversity, or at least the component represented by forest

songbirds. We plan to develop this work into a manuscript later in 2013 for submission to a journal such as Ecological Indicators or Biological Conservation.

Figure 12: Relationship between equality of representation with respect to remote-sensed biodiversity surrogates (x-axis) and the variance in the proportional abundances among 119 songbird species (y-axis), evaluated for 100,000 randomly generated protected areas networks constructed according to the BEACONS methodology. Each network covered 20% of the area of the Arctic Ocean Drainage basin within Brandt's (2009) boreal zone. The most representative networks are those with the lowest distance metric, and these networks had had the lowest the Standard Deviation of proportional species' abundances (SD Pi). As Distance increased (and ecological dissimilarity increased, the representation of species in the networks became more uneven. It follows that the Distance metric is good surrogate for avian biodiversity.

2.5 Waterfowl Modelling

BAM expanded its taxonomic scope to include certain waterfowl species through collaboration between Cumming and Marcel Darveau of Ducks Unlimited Canada who is a member of the Technical Committee. The initiative has been independently funded through NSERC Industrial scholarships supporting two PhD students, Christian Roy and Nicole Barker. Their theses focus on developing sophisticated statistical models based on a long-term Waterfowl Breeding Population and Habitat Survey (BPOP) conducted by the USFWS and CWS. Through these students, we have developed deeper connections with other DUC researchers, the USFWS Division of Migratory Bird Management, and the USGS Patuxent Wildlife Research Center, as well as waterfowl researchers and managers in Environment Canada. BAM provided technical support by funding geospatial data processing in Cumming's lab. This work represents an initial effort to expand the taxonomic scope of BAM beyond forest passerines.

2.5.1 Critical review of the BPOP dataset from a modelling perspective

Our intended applications of the BPOP dataset range from high-spatial resolution Species Distribution Models of species densities, and spatially-structured, coupled population-dynamics models using annual weather and other covariates, coupled with models of the detection process. Because the data were not collected with these uses in mind, Barker conducted an extensive review and survey of the sampling regime and data contents to assess its potential use in habitat models for informing habitat conservation decisions. She examined the contents of the database and worked with database managers in USFWS to correct many errors. The data are organised in a four-level hierarchical structure of which the smallest scale is the segment, which corresponds to a roughly 30km by 0.4km survey transect in which waterfowl are counted by aerial survey. One basic result of this work is a segment-resolution map of total sampling effort over the entire region surveyed (Figure 13). The review also highlights important research challenges in modelling species' abundances at fine scales, and presents potential solutions. A draft will be submitted to the U.S. Fish & Wildlife service in April 2013 for fact-checking and review, and a manuscript will also be prepared.

Figure 13: Apparent survey effort from 1955-2011, indicated by the number of years a segment appears in the database. Darker colours indicate more years and lighter colours indicate fewer years. The prairie pothole region, the McKenzie delta and parts of Alaska have been sampled most consistently from 1955 while the eastern region and some boreal areas have been sampled much less frequently, beginning in the 1990s or later.

2.5.2 Distribution models for waterfowl species

Using 10 years of recent BPOP data, Barker used Boosted Regression Trees to model species abundances in relation to 78 biophysical variables obtained primarily from the BAMs biophysical database assembled over the past seven years (Barker, Cumming and Darveau 2013). The choice of model methodology followed BAM's recent approaches as exemplified by Stralberg's models of songbird species for climate change scenarios as described elsewhere in this report and those of Cumming et al. (in review). Model predictions were then generated, assisted by PostGIS raster-vector technology developed in Cumming's lab, and then mapped over most of Canada (Figure 14). Model predictions were overlaid with NatureServe range maps (Ridgely et al. 2003) to assess concordance. The results of refined versions of these models are intended for use Ducks Unlimited Canada to prioritise areas for conservation network planning. Barker will also provide these results to a CWS assessment of landscape ecosystem services.

2.5.3 Waterfowl population dynamics

Christian Roy has used hierarchical Bayesian state-space models to study population dynamics of several species of ducks in the western part of the survey area. The data are spatially aggregated into 33 strata within four ecozones (Prairies, Boreal Plains, Taiga Plains and Boreal Shield). The models account for density dependence and detection error. Population growth rates were modelled as functions of density, and also of seasonal precipitation in the local and adjacent ecozones. Effects of seasonality differed among species, and there was evidence of temporary migration or overflight of populations between ecozones as a function of drought in the south. A manuscript describing this work is in preparation. These results were presented at the 6th North American Duck Symposium (Roy et al. 2013), along with several other talks and posters by these students (Roy et al 2013; Barker, Roy, Cumming and Darveau 2013).

Figure 14: Predicted species densities of waterfowl from preliminary Boosted Regression Trees models are shown for five species. Models were selected using 78 climatic and landscape-based predictor variables. The last map (bottom right) represents the total predicted abundance of 17 species of waterfowl, based on the predictions of individual species' models. Spatial resolution of the maps is 300 arcseconds or approximately 100 km².

2.6 Collaboration with avian ecologists and communication

In addition to the collaboration amongst team members and affiliates within the Canadian and US governments, the BAM team welcomes opportunities for collaboration and actively engages other experts in avian ecology and conservation. In the past year, the team has drawn upon expertise within the Technical Committee to provide critical comments on the manuscript addressing avian sampling protocols. Some of the Technical Committee also participated in a webinar discussion in February 2012 about the use of automated recording units for avian monitoring, addressing issues including research design, sharing data, and collaborating on field projects in 2013. A funding opportunity with the US Fish and Wildlife Service to address climate change impacts on boreal birds in the Alaska/Yukon region is being pursued.

BAM, in conjunction with staff from the Cornell Laboratory of Ornithology, developed a symposium for the North American Ornithological Conference in August 2012. The symposium titled “Assessing bird populations at regional to continental scales: results from innovative approaches to data intensive analyses of North American birds” presented the research findings that are beginning to emerge from the new analytical approaches that are being developed to analyze the large repositories of non-standardised avian data that are being compiled across North America. Twelve speakers, including 3 from the BAM team presented results of recent research to approximately 150 attendees.

2.6.1 Communication of results

We redesigned the BAM website to highlight our new results, to improve access to analytical results, and to provide new users with a better understanding of the BAM project. We expanded the section describing methodologies used to address various biases in point count surveys (avian detection, roadside detection, and geographic and habitat biases). We revised estimates of avian population densities at a national scale using our refined methodologies and presented regional-scale density estimates from the Alberta Forest Songbird Information System (AFSIS). The site is designed so users can download the density estimates and habitat associations (at national or Alberta scale) by individual species. We posted distribution maps for 88 species showing relative habitat suitability and comparing these results to the NatureServe range maps.

Under the Methods section of the website, we provide recommendations for improving point count survey protocols, and describe methods developed to standardise national Forest Resource Inventory (FRI) data (CASFRI) for use in other modelling exercises. We provide some additional descriptions of the avian and biophysical databases that provide the basis for BAM analyses. The Conservation section outlines some of the collaborative partnerships where the BAM project has been able to provide data or expertise to further avian conservation goals. Efforts to provide Interactive mapping products to display avian and biophysical data and results (which would give users control over which information layers to display, and at what scale) are underway, but progress to data has been limited as our efforts have focused on updating the database with new datasets. BAM has received positive comments on our new website from avian managers including the PIF national coordinator.

3.0 Summary of Applications of BAM Project Results

Details of the application of BAM results from 2012-13 to conservation and management efforts are presented throughout the preceding sections. Here we present a summary of those efforts for ease of reference, as well as describe other known applications of BAM data, data products and analyses that occurred in 2012-13. Applications are additive to those documented in previous BAM reports.

Boreal bird monitoring – Joint Oil Sands Monitoring (JOSM):

- Application of regional bird-habitat models to identification of gaps in habitat coverage and design of early sampling to support effects assessment monitoring program for landbirds under JOSM.
- Foundational meetings towards active collaboration to build updated bird-habitat models for application in trend monitoring and effects assessment monitoring by JOSM partners (EC, ABMI, EMCLA).
- Adoption of standard protocols for landbird surveys developed by BAM in JOSM.

Boreal bird monitoring – NWT proposed National Wildlife Areas:

- Provision of standardized data for precision analysis required for monitoring design.

Species at Risk recovery planning:

- Generation of national models of Canada Warbler using detailed stand type/age information from national standardized Forest Resource Inventory produce (CASFRI).
- Generation of detailed regional models of Canada Warbler at scale of province of Alberta using additional provincial datasets to provide a planning tool for regional land-use and cumulative effects assessment.
- Initial comparisons of variation in habitat selection across boreal-wide species ranges for Canada Warbler (and 2 other species).
- Establishment at both national and regional levels of proof-of-concept models that will be applied in the future to additional species models.
- Results are additive to previous year's results on regional and national models of abundance, distribution, and habitat associations for Olive-sided Flycatcher, Rusty Blackbird, and Canada Warbler at national and regional scale.
- Ongoing discussion with CWS leads for recovery of Canada Warbler, Rusty Blackbird and Olive-sided Flycatcher on how BAM can further support recovery and action planning efforts, including identification of critical habitat.

Protected Areas Network design:

- Application of species distribution models generated by BAM in joint project between Canadian Boreal Forest Agreement and Boreal Ecosystem Analysis for Conservation Networks). Results were used to validate the representativeness of a proposed set of protected areas across the Canadian boreal forest for boreal songbirds.

Research on climate change impacts:

- Generation of research reports on the impacts of climate change on available climatic niche for species from current to 2100 for species with boreal-wide ranges and dominant ranges in Alaska. Reports produced for Alaska USFWS and Environment Canada.

Implementation of BCR strategies and science for BCR planning:

- Completion of manuscript on priority areas analysis (Element 7) for BCR 6 – Boreal Taiga Plains by Environment Canada (Mahon) and BAM. (Analysis reported in previous BAM report 2009-12).
- Completion of manuscript using PIF methodology to step forward BCR objectives to the sub-regional scale and assess future scenarios to achieve BCR objectives in the Alberta Pacific Forest Industries Forest Management Area. (Analysis reported in previous BAM report 2009-12; collaboration between ALPac, EC, BAM and others).

4.0 Project Communications

Presentations 2012 – 2013

Bayne, E.M. 2013. Use of Automated Recording Unit data within BAM and Beyond. Presentation to the BAM Technical Committee by conference call. 6 February 2013. Edmonton, Alberta.

Barker, N.K.S., C. Roy, S. Cumming, & M. Darveau. 2013. New approaches isolate climatic effects on population dynamics. Presentation at the Ecology and Conservation of North American Waterfowl conference – Memphis, Tennessee. January 30, 2013.

Barker, N.K.S., S. Cumming, & M. Darveau. 2013. Predicting species' distributions and abundances with climate and landcover. Presentation at the Ecology and Conservation of North American Waterfowl conference – Memphis, Tennessee. January 28, 2013. doi: 10.6084/m9.figshare.156365

Barker, N.K.S., S. Cumming, & M. Darveau. 2013. Improving waterfowl population estimates using hierarchical models: A new approach. Poster at the Ecology and Conservation of North American Waterfowl conference – Memphis, Tennessee. January 30, 2013.

Barker, N.K.S. Waterfowl population modeling. 2012. Presentation at the Ducks Unlimited Canada Eastern Regional Meeting, Ottawa, Ontario. September 19, 2012.

Barker, N.K.S., C. Roy, S.G. Cumming, and M. Darveau. 2012. Predicting waterfowl occurrence and distribution: Effects of climate and habitat. Poster at the North American Ornithological Conference. Vancouver, British Columbia. August 17-18, 2012.

Cumming, S.G., and F.K.A. Schmiegelow. 2012. Integrating avian habitat models and conservation planning across North America's boreal forest. Presentation in conference symposium titled "Assessing bird populations at regional to continental scales: results from innovative approaches to data-intensive analyses of North American birds." August 15, 2012. Vancouver, Canada.

Mahon, C. L., E. M. Bayne, P. Sólymos, S. M. Matsuoka, M. Carlson, and E. Dzus. 2012. Does expected future habitat condition support proposed population objectives for boreal landbirds? Ecological Society of America. August 7, 2012. Portland, USA.

Mahon, C. L., E. M. Bayne, P. Sólymos, S. M. Matsuoka, M. Carlson, and E. Dzus. 2012. The five elements process: can future habitat supply meet proposed population objectives for boreal

- landbirds? August 12, 2012. Partners in Flight Science Committee. Vancouver, Canada.
- Matsuoka, S., P. Sólymos, D. Stralberg, T. Fontaine, E. Bayne, F. Schmiegelow, S. Song, S. Cumming. 2012. Estimating boreal bird densities and population sizes from non-standardized point counts: making the most of a messy situation. Presentation in conference symposium titled “Assessing bird populations at regional to continental scales: results from innovative approaches to data-intensive analyses of North American birds.” August 15, 2012. Vancouver, Canada.
- Matsuoka, S., P. Sólymos, D. Stralberg, T. Fontaine, E. Bayne, F. Schmiegelow, S. Song, S. Cumming. 2012. Estimating boreal bird densities and population sizes from non-standardized point counts: making the most of a messy situation. Alaska Bird Conference. Oct. 22, 2012.
- Roy, C., S.G. Cumming, M. Darveau. 2013. Climate Influences on the Spatial Dynamics of Waterfowl Populations in the Boreal Forest, Ecology and Conservation of North American Waterfowl conference – Memphis, Tennessee. January 2013.
- Roy, C., E.J.B. McIntire, S.G. Cumming, M. Darveau, and N.K.S. Barker. 2012. Using the waterfowl breeding population and habitat survey to identify spatial population dynamics in boreal ducks. Presentation in conference symposium titled “Assessing bird populations at regional to continental scales: results from innovative approaches to data-intensive analyses of North American birds.” August 15, 2012. Vancouver, Canada.
- Schmiegelow, F.K.A. 2012. An odyssey of boreal bird research and conservation in Canada. Invited plenary presentation to North American Ornithological Conference – Vancouver. August 14, 2012. Vancouver, Canada.
- Schmiegelow, F.K.A. 2013. Science-based support for broad-scale conservation of boreal systems: the BEACONS and BAM Projects. Presented to the Wildlife and Landscape Science Directorate by conference call. Jan. 23, 2013. Whitehorse, Yukon.
- Song, S.J. 2013. Boreal Avian Modelling Project: Update to Species at Risk Managers by conference call. Jan 8, 2013. Edmonton, Alberta.
- Song, S.J. 2013. Boreal Avian Modelling Project: Update to Migratory Bird Managers by conference call. Jan 9, 2013. Edmonton, Alberta.
- Stralberg, D. 2012. Projecting effects of climate change on boreal bird distribution. Presentation to the University of Alberta GIS Day. Edmonton, AB. Nov. 13, 2012.
- Stralberg, D., S. Matsuoka, P. Sólymos, T. Fontaine, E. Bayne, F. Schmiegelow, S. Song, S. Cumming, C. Handel. Preliminary projections of Rusty Blackbird responses to future climate change across the boreal forest. 2012. Presentation (remotely) by S. Matsuoka to the 3rd Workshop of the International Rusty Blackbird Working Group. Oct. 16-18, 2012. Plymouth, MA.
- Stralberg, D., P. Sólymos, E. Bayne, S. Matsuoka, F. Schmiegelow, S. Cumming, T. Fontaine, S. Song. 2012. Beyond distribution: projecting climate-change effects on boreal bird density patterns. Presentation in conference symposium titled “Assessing bird populations at regional to continental scales: results from innovative approaches to data-intensive analyses of North American birds.” August 15, 2012. Vancouver, Canada.

Publications 2012 – 2013

- Mayor, S.J., Cahill, J.F., He, F., Sólymos, P. & Boutin, S. (2012): Regional boreal biodiversity peaks at intermediate human disturbance. *Nature Communications*, 3: 1142, DOI: 10.1038/ncomms2145
- Sólymos, P., Burton, C, Herbers, J., Boutin, S. & Schieck, J. (2013, in press): Is accurate location information necessary for repeatability in field based ecology? *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*
- Walker, S. C., Guénard, G., Sólymos, P. & Legendre, P. (2012): Multiple-table data in R with the

multitable package. Journal of Statistical Software, 51(8): 1-38.

Publications (submitted, in review, or in revision 2012 – 2013)

Bayne, E.M., J. A. Campbell. Submitted to Journal of Field Ornithology Sept. 2012. Sound propagation parallel versus perpendicular to narrow roads in forests: implications for avian point count surveys?

Cumming, S. G., D. Stralberg, K. Lefevre, P. Solymos, E. Bayne, S. Fang, T. Fontaine, D. Mazerolle, F. Schmiegelow, and S. J. Song. Accepted with minor revisions 13 March 2013. Climate and vegetation hierarchically structure continental patterns of songbird distribution and abundance in the Canadian boreal region. *Ecography*.

Matsuoka, S. M., C. L. Mahon, P. Sólymos, E. M. Bayne, P. C. Fontaine, and C. M. Handel. Submitted to the Auk Nov. 21, 2012. In revision. There and back again? Revisiting common standards for conducting point-count surveys to estimate breeding abundance of terrestrial birds in northern North America.

Sólymos, P., S. M. Matsuoka, E. M. Bayne, S. G. Cumming, D. Stralberg, F. K. A. Schmiegelow, and S. J. Song. In review. Using a removal model to adjust point-count surveys for variation in the duration of the counting duration. *Auk* (Original submission to the Auk Jan 2012).

Sólymos, P., S. M. Matsuoka, E. M. Bayne, S. R. Lele, P. Fontaine, S. G. Cumming, and D. Stralberg, F. Schmiegelow, S. Song. 2012b. Submitted Nov. 15, 2012. In review. Calibrating indices of avian density from non-standardized survey data: making the most of a messy situation. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*.

Publications (in preparation 2012 – 2013)

Ball, J. R., P. Sólymos, and E. M. Bayne. In preparation. Habitat associations of Canada Warbler *Cardellina canadensis* in Alberta. Journal TBD.

Barker, N.K.S. 2013. Relative abundance of pairs of cavity, ground, and over-water nesting ducks in Canada. Unpublished report, Université Laval, Ducks Unlimited Canada, and Boreal Avian Modelling Project, Québec, QC.

Barker, N.K.S., S. M. Slattery, S. Cumming, M. Darveau. In preparation. Predictive species distribution models for species aggregations: Effectiveness for conservation planning. *PLoS ONE*. Barker, N.K.S. In preparation. Expanded application of the Waterfowl Breeding Population and Habitat Survey: A guide for secondary users. Journal TBD.

Cumming, S.G., R. Drever, and M. Houle. A representation gap analysis of forest tree species in the Canadian boreal region. *Canadian Journal of Forest Research*.

Desrochers, A., S. Cumming, D. Lévesque, N. Barker. Networking Automated Recording Units using wireless technology. *in Prep for Journal of Field Ornithology*.

Matsuoka, S. M., E. M. Bayne, P. Sólymos, D. Stralberg, S. J. Song, F. Schmiegelow, and S. Cumming. In preparation. Estimating population sizes of landbirds breeding across the Nearctic boreal forest zone. *Ecological Applications*.

Matsuoka, S. M., P. Sólymos, E. M. Bayne, and P. C. Fontaine. In preparation. Roadside bias in point-count surveys of boreal forest birds: prevalence, effect size, and relationship to detection

distance. Biological Conservation.

Mahon, C. L., E. M. Bayne, P. Sólymos, S. M. Matsuoka, M. Carlson, and E. Dzus. In preparation. Does expected future landscape condition support proposed population objectives for boreal birds? Forest Ecology and Management.

Mahon, C. L., T. Habib, D. Farr, T. Mahon, E. M. Bayne, and T. Fontaine. In preparation. Priority area assessment for landbirds in Bird Conservation Region 6-Boreal Taiga Plains using two measures of area occupied. Journal TBD.

Stralberg, D., E. Bayne, P. Sólymos, S. Matsuoka, X. Wang, A. Hamann, T. Fontaine, Cumming, S. G, and F. Schmiegelow. Projected changes in climatic suitability of boreal avifauna across multiple sources of uncertainty. Journal TBD.

Stralberg, D., F. Schmiegelow, E. Bayne, S. Matsuoka, P. Sólymos, S. Cumming, C. Handel, and S. Song. Conservation priorities for boreal avifauna in changing climate. Journal TBD.

Technical Reports

Alberta Biodiversity Monitoring Institute (ABMI). 2012. The Status of Landbirds in Alberta's Boreal Plains Ecozone: Preliminary Assessment. Edmonton.

<http://www.abmi.ca/abmi/reports/reports.jsp?categoryId=163>

Huggard, D. and C. Machtans. 2013. Precision Analysis of Bird Trend Monitoring in NWT Proposed National Wildlife Areas. Report by Apophenia Consulting and Canadian Wildlife Service.

http://www.borealbirds.ca/library/index.php/technical_reports

5.0 Project Management

5.1 Steering Committee, Project Staff and Affiliates

The project Steering Committee consists of Drs. Fiona Schmiegelow, Erin Bayne, Steve Cumming, and Samantha Song. Collectively, they hold responsibility for project coordination, including staff management, liaison with project partners and the Technical Committee, and overall project direction.

Team members this year included:

- Database Manager (Trish Fontaine)
- Project Coordinator (Catherine Rostron 0.5 FTE until March 2013)
- Statistical Ecologist (Dr. Péter Sólymos 0.5 FTE)
- Project Affiliate (Dr. C. Lisa Mahon, Environment Canada)
- Project Affiliate (Steve Matsuoka U. S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Alaska Office)
- PhD Candidate with Drs. Bayne and Schmiegelow (Diana Stralberg)
- PhD Candidate with Dr. Cumming (Nicole Barker) in association with Ducks Unlimited Canada
- PhD Candidate with Dr. Cumming (Christian Roy)

5.2 Technical Committee

Our Technical Committee (TC) continues to provide independent scientific advice on project direction and results. We would like to thank Peter Blancher, Environment Canada, who retired from Environment Canada this year, for his past involvement with the TC. Our Technical Committee members are:

Marcel Darveau, Ducks Unlimited / Université Laval
Jean-Luc DesGranges, Environment Canada
André Desrochers, Université Laval
Pierre Drapeau, Université du Québec à Montréal
Charles Francis, Environment Canada
Colleen Handel, United States Geological Survey, Alaska Science Center
Keith Hobson, Environment Canada
Craig Machtans, Environment Canada
Julienne Morissette, Ducks Unlimited Canada
Gerald Niemi, University of Minnesota – Duluth;
Rob Rempel, Ontario Ministry of Natural Resources / Lakehead University
Stuart Slattery, Ducks Unlimited Canada
Phil Taylor, Acadia University
Steve Van Wilgenburg, Environment Canada
Lisa Venier, Natural Resources Canada
Pierre Vernier, University of British Columbia
Marc-André Villard, Université de Moncton

5.3 Additional Support

Many additional people provide time and expertise to BAM project activities. In particular, we would like to recognise the contributions of the following individuals:

Connie Downes (Environment Canada): BBS data
Mélina Houle (Université Laval): spatial data analyst
Marie-Anne Hudson (Environment Canada): BBS data
Bénédictte Kenmei (Université Laval): computer programming
Justine Kummer (University of Alberta): database and website assistance
Rasim Latifovic (Canada Centre for Remote Sensing, CCRS, Natural Resources Canada): for land cover data
Mélanie-Louise Leblanc (Université Laval): programming of statistical summaries
Dan McKenney (Great Lakes Forest Centre, Natural Resources Canada): custom-interpreted climate data
Paul Morrill (Web Services): website design & programming
Pia Papadol (Great Lakes Forest Centre, Natural Resources Canada): custom-interpreted climate data
Sheila Potter (Blue Chair Designs): graphic design and website design and development
Pierre Racine (Université Laval): GIS programming
Xianli Wang (University of Alberta): climate data projections.

5.4 Partnerships

To achieve its objectives, BAM continues to rely on partnerships on many levels, including our data contributors, our Technical Committee and its members, our funders, and the various collaborative efforts described in the preceding sections. The BAM project would not exist without the generous contributions of its funding and data partners.

5.4.1 Funding partners

We are grateful to the following organisations that have provided funding to the BAM Project since its initiation:

Founding organisations and funders

Environment Canada
University of Alberta
BEACONs

Additional financial supporters

United States Fish and Wildlife Service,

- Neotropical Migratory Bird Conservation Act Grants Program
- Landscape Conservation Cooperatives

Alberta Conservation Association
Alberta Pacific Forest Industries Inc.
Climate Change and Emissions Corporation
Government of Canada (Vanier Scholarship)
Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC)
National Fish and Wildlife Foundation (NFWF)
Université Laval

Past financial supporters

Alberta Biodiversity Monitoring Institute
Alberta Innovates Technology Futures
Alberta Land-use Framework (Government of Alberta)
Canadian Boreal Initiative
Canada Foundation for Innovation
Canada Research Chairs program
Ducks Unlimited Canada
Environmental Studies Research Fund
Forest Products Association of Canada
Fonds québécois de la recherche sur la nature et les technologies
Geomatics for Informed Decisions (GEOIDE)
Killam Trusts (Memorial scholarship to Stralberg)
Sustainable Forest Management Network

5.4.2 Data partners

The following institutions and individuals generously provided or facilitated provision of bird and environmental data to the Boreal Avian Modelling Project.

Institutions

Acadia University, Alaska Bird Observatory, Alaska Department of Fish and Game, Alaska Natural Heritage Program, Alberta Biodiversity Monitoring Institute, Alberta Pacific Forest Industries Inc., AMEC Earth & Environmental, AREVA Resources Canada Inc., Avian Knowledge Network, AXYS Environmental Consulting Ltd., Bighorn Wildlife Technologies Ltd., Bird Studies Canada, Breeding Bird Survey (coordinated in Canada by Environment Canada), BC Breeding Bird Atlas, Canadian Natural Resources Ltd., Canfor Corporation, Daishowa Marubeni International Ltd, Ducks Unlimited Canada, Environment Canada (Canadian Wildlife Service and Science and Technology Branch), Global Land Cover Facility, Golder Associates Ltd., Government of British Columbia, Government of Yukon, Hinton Wood Products, Hydro-Québec Équipement, Kluane Ecosystem Monitoring Project, Komex International Ltd., Louisiana Pacific Canada Ltd., Manitoba Breeding Bird Atlas, Manitoba Hydro, Manitoba Model Forest Inc., Manning Diversified Forest Products Ltd., Maritimes Consultants Ltd., Matrix Solutions Inc. Environment & Engineering, MEG Energy Corp., Mirkwood Ecological Consultants Ltd., Natural Resources Canada (Canada Centre for Remote Sensing and Canadian Forest Service), NatureCounts, Nature Serve, Numerical Terradynamic Simulation Group, Ontario Breeding Bird Atlas, Ontario Ministry of Natural Resources, OPTI Canada Inc., PanCanadian Petroleum Limited, Parks Canada (Mountain National Parks Avian Monitoring database), Petro Canada, Principal Wildlife Resource Consulting, Regroupement QuébecOiseaux, Rio Alto Resources International Inc., Saskatchewan Environment, Shell Canada Limited, Suncor Energy Inc., Tembec Industries Inc., Tolko Industries Ltd., US Fish and Wildlife Service, U.S. Bureau of Land Management; U.S. Department of Defense; U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service; U.S. Geological Survey, Alaska Science Center; U.S. National Park Service; Université de Moncton; Université du Québec à Montréal; Université du Québec en Abitibi-Témiscamingue; Université Laval; University of Alaska, Fairbanks; University of Alberta; University of British Columbia; University of Guelph; University of New Brunswick; University of Northern British Columbia; URSUS Ecosystem Management Ltd.; West Fraser Timber Co. Ltd.; Weyerhaeuser Company Ltd.; Wildlife Resource Consulting Services MB Inc.

Individuals

K. Aitken, A. Ajmi, B. Andres, J. Ball, E. Bayne, P. Belagus, S. Bennett, R. Berger, M. Betts, J. Bielech, A. Bismanis, R. Brown, M. Cadman, D. Collister, M. Cranny, S. Cumming, L. Darling, M. Darveau, C. De La Mare, A. Desrochers, T. Diamond, M. Donnelly, C. Downs, P. Drapeau, C. Duane, B. Dube, D. Dye, R. Eccles, P. Farrington, R. Fernandes, M. Flamme, D. Fortin, K. Foster, M. Gill, T. Gotthardt, N. Guldager, R. Hall, C. Handel, S. Hannon, B. Harrison, C. Harwood, J. Herbers, K. Hobson, M-A. Hudson, L. Imbeau, P. Johnstone, V. Keenan, K. Koch, M. Laker, S. Lapointe, R. Latifovic, R. Lauzon, M. Leblanc, L. Ledrew, J. Lemaitre, D. Lepage, C. McIntyre, B. MacCallum, P. MacDonell, C. Machtans, C. McIntyre, M. McGovern, D. McKenney, S. Mason, L. Morgantini, J. Morton, G. Niemi, T. Nudds, P. Papadol, M. Phinney,

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